

Assessing the Trustworthiness of Large Language Models on Domain-specific Questions

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Abstract. Using prompt-engineering and retrieval augmented generation, we can leverage pre-trained Large Language Models to answer domain-specific questions relying on information from textual sources. In this work, we discuss how to assess the trustworthiness of a module that performs such task: how to build a large, representative, and unbiased dataset of questions/answers by automatically generating variations and which metrics to compute. We apply the methodology to a use-case where a smart wheelchair provides answers about its functioning, presenting experimental results on a dataset of more than 1000 questions.

Keywords: Natural Language Processing · ChatGPT · Trustworthy LLMs · Assisted mobility · Human-Machine Interaction · RAG.

1 Introduction

The recent boost of innovation in Large Language Models (LLMs), like ChatGPT from OpenAI,³ is impacting our society as a whole. For instance, in the workplace, more and more text authoring tasks are supported or even completely automatized by LLMs. More natural and intuitive speech-based Human-Machine interfaces (HMI), like those embedded in most current operating systems, are another prominent application of LLMs. The Horizon Europe project REXASI-PRO⁴ (REliable & eXplAinable Swarm Intelligence for People with Reduced mObility) is developing trustworthy-by-design tools to help people with reduced mobility; in this context, LLMs may assist users to answer domain-specific questions, e.g., about the functioning of their smart wheelchair (we will focus on this use-case) or about the surroundings.

Like most Deep Learning methods, LLMs represent black-boxes for their users. Anecdotally, they work well, yet they do not provide guarantees on their performance when answering domain-specific questions [4]. How can we trust that their answers are correct and useful? How can we trust them to declare their ignorance when not provided with enough information to answer a specific question? Trustworthiness of software components relies on many factors, some of which are subjective to the users [14]. In this work, we focus on three main features:

³ <https://chat.openai.com>

⁴ <https://rexasi-pro.spindoxlabs.com>

Correctness: are answers correct (i.e., contain no invalid or irrelevant information, neither miss important information)?

Robustness: are answers robust to small variations that generate semantically similar questions, like it would be expected from human interlocutors?

Explainability: can LLM-based modules explain why they provide a particular answer, and identify the source of information in the original context?

As **main contribution**, we present a general methodology to answer these questions and assess how well an LLM performs on a specific domain. In particular, we discuss how to define appropriate metrics for the target properties listed above, and a dataset⁵ of representative questions from users, to assess the trustworthiness of the LLM-based module.

The paper is organized as following: in Section 2, we describe related works; in Section 3, we present the methodology (how to use an LLM to answer domain-specific queries and how to perform a static assessment); in Section 4, we apply the methodology to answer questions about smart wheelchair functioning using ChatGPT, presenting the results in Section 5.

2 Related Work

Several works have addressed trustworthiness-related topics with respect to LLMs, either from the high-level perspective [10] or discussing a particular aspect focusing on a precisely defined set of research questions [7, 12, 13, 3]. Although trustworthiness as an umbrella term is a bit fuzzy and encompasses different things, the research mainly focalizes on topics of reliability [12, 19, 7, 4, 13, 9], robustness [19], consistency [3, 9, 15], and accuracy [4, 15], to measure the performance of LLMs in question answering (QA) setup. As the focus of this work is on a QA task, we limit the scope and leave out of consideration other studies focusing, e.g., on robustness and reliability checks of LLM code generation [12, 19]. Despite different LLMs have been considered in QA-related works on the topic, most of the studies focus on ChatGPT [12, 4, 15, 3, 2].

With respect to previous work, this study exhibits two main differences. First, the majority of previous works resort to prompting as the main strategy to assess model reliability [13, 7, 12, 2]. Unlike them, we fix the prompt and devise the evaluation framework based on data augmentation. Additionally, contrary to existing works which test ChatGPT robustness using sentence-level and character-level adversarial attacks [12], we ensure that the augmented data preserves the semantics of the original instance. Moreover, unlike Es et al. [2], we use question variants and explainability based on informative sentences and page numbers, although, differently from them, we require ground truth and we do not assess the quality of retrieved content, as it is out of scope of this work.

Second, most of the previous works rely on available datasets (either entirely [13], or sampling from these randomly [12], or curating specifically tailored datasets, encompassing diverse domains related to general topics (e.g.,

⁵ Available at <https://github.com/SandraMNE/TWALLM>

Fig. 1: Pipeline to answer a contextualized question using an LLM. The database of chunks is built during preprocessing, and shared by all queries to add domain-specific context to the prompt.

Wikipedia [7]) as well as particular domains, such as recreation, medicine, (social) science, technology, law, history [12]. Very few previous studies constructed a dataset from scratch, all focusing on medical domain [4, 15], but presented contradictory findings. Unlike these studies which rely only on descriptive assessment and categorization, we propose a more systematic procedure. In particular, inspired by the claims that question difficulty significantly affects accuracy [15], we devise our own, more fine-grained, question categorization. Additionally, our methodology can be applied to any use-case and is domain-agnostic.

3 Methodology

In our application context, LLMs answer users’ questions related to a specific domain. Users are free to ask anything but should not expect informative answers when these would require information not provided by source documents. We consider state-less interactions with users asking single questions without follow-ups.

3.1 System

This section describes the pipeline, illustrated in Fig. 1, to answer contextualized questions using an LLM. We assume the availability of an LLM, based on a transformer model and pre-trained on a large generic textual datasets, that generates output text for an input query x . We also assume that answering should rely on information contained on a source document D (or *knowledge base*), such as a travel book, an event program, or, like in the use-case presented in Section 4, a manual. The pipeline is based on prompt engineering supported by retrieval augmentation, passing relevant parts of the source document through the input query: given a question q , we build input $x(q, D)$, and evaluate it with the LLM.

Source document preprocessing LLMs may have a limit on the input size; for instance, the version of ChatGPT used in Section 4, limits the input to about 3000 characters. In order to handle larger source documents, we use Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) to select the most relevant parts to answer a question [8]. At first, to speed up queries, we preprocess the source document:

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1 You are role. Your goal is to give concise and informative answers based solely
2 on the given DOCUMENTS. Please reply to the question using only the information
3 present in the DOCUMENTS below. If the answer is not contained within the text
4 above, reply politely that the information is not in the knowledge base. You
5 must only use information from the given DOCUMENTS. Use an unbiased and
6 journalistic tone and answer only with the essential information. Do not repeat
7 text. If you don't know the answer, just say that you don't know, don't try to
8 make up an answer.
9 DOCUMENTS:
10 - chunk 1
11     ⋮
12 - chunk n
13 QUESTION:
14 question
15 For every sentence inside DOCUMENTS, detect each sentence and assign a score
16 between 0 and 1 that reflects how informative it is to answering the question.
17 Return the answer to the question and a markdown table that shows the sentences
18 with score greater than 0.1, where each row has two data entry, one is the
19 sentence, and the other is the score associated to it.

```

Fig. 2: The prompt. Green boxes are domain-specific substitutions shared across questions, while blue boxes have values specific to a question; see Section 4 for an example of “role”.

1. we import the document as a text string (e.g., extracting text from paragraphs and tables of a PDF file);
2. we divide the text into chunks (500-character long, non-overlapping), such that k of them fit in the prompt of the LLM (in practice, $5 \leq k \leq 10$);
3. for each chunk, we compute its embedding using the LLM (or another method) and store it in a vector database, where we can search using appropriate distance functions.

Then, at run-time, we query the vector database to retrieve chunks that are semantically similar to the question, selecting the k nearest chunks in the embedding space. The chunking process can be adapted to the particular use case and is not among the main concerns of this paper.

Prompt creation We define a prompt that asks the LLM to answer the question relying solely on the retrieved chunks. To promote explainability and transparency, we additionally ask the LLM to list the most useful (for generating the answer) sentences contained in the chunks, and to assign them a score. The prompt, reported in Fig. 2, consists of four parts: the *prefix* describing the scope of the query, the model’s response behaviour, and the generation constraints and requirements (lines 1–8); the *context* with the most pertinent chunks to the question (9–12); the *question* (13–14); the *suffix* asking to report the most informative sentences (15–19).

Inference We pass the prompt to the LLM, which outputs two parts: the answer to the question and the table with the most informative sentences. We forward the answer to the user (as speech or text), and use the second part to provide supporting information depending on the use-case, e.g., by highlighting the most relevant parts of the original document.

3.2 Assessment

We want to assess how trustworthy the presented system answers users’ questions. For this, we build a dataset of questions and answers, and define appropriate metrics.

Questions categories The dataset needs to be representative of possible users’ questions. In particular, questions should: *(a)* touch different topics; *(b)* exhibit different complexity w.r.t. answer availability (that is, being answerable using concrete information found in a single paragraph, or being answerable using cross-paragraph information, or only partially answerable, or even unanswerable); *(c)* exhibit different complexity w.r.t. question formulation (that is, represent different levels of complexity from a linguistic perspective). We define a total of $C = 8$ categories:

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- C1 Closed-form yes-no question
 - C2 Closed-form question with non-binary answer
 - C3 Simple open question (answer can be found in single paragraph)
 - C4 Complex open question (answer can be found, but not in a single paragraph)
 - C5 Ambiguous/conditional open question (the answer may not be found)
 - C6 Question with negation
 - C7 Question with appositives
 - C8 Question with idiomatic expressions
-

Augmentation For each question, we generate M variations that cover semantically equivalent ways for users to ask for the same information, using the following techniques:

Synonym-replacement [5] is a lexical transformation technique that substitutes words with semantically similar counterparts. The objective is to maintain the overall meaning of the sentence while introducing variation in vocabulary. The substitution strategies can rely on lexical databases such as Wordnet to find synonyms [18], and/or strategies that use embedding-based word similarity [16], either exploiting embeddings from traditional models (e.g., word2vec, GloVe) or contextual embeddings (e.g., BERT, RoBERTa).

Back-translation is a popular technique in NLP and machine translation, introduced by Sennrich et al. in 2016 [11]. Back-translation serves as a form of data augmentation, creating synthetic examples by translating source sentences into target languages and then back into the source language.

Paraphrasing aims to capture the inherent meaning of a sentence while presenting it using alternative words or structures. In NLP, paraphrasing models are typically either trained using large datasets that contain pairs of sentences with equivalent meanings, or use pre-trained models fine-tuned for the paraphrasing tasks.

By augmenting the dataset, we are able to (a) perform a more robust analysis with larger statistical significance; (b) measure the robustness of LLMs when answering semantically equivalent questions.

Data The dataset contains N original questions $q_0^k, k = 1, \dots, N$ and their automatically generated variations q_1^k, \dots, q_M^k . For each question, we record the following information from human experts and from the LLM inference:

Field	Description	Source	For all variations?
\tilde{c}^k	question category	experts	only original question
\tilde{a}_0^k	answer	experts	only original question
a_i^k	answer	LLM	for each $i = 0, \dots, M$
$\tilde{e}_A^k, \tilde{e}_B^k, \tilde{e}_C^k$	correctness of LLM answer	experts	only original question
$\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_0^k = \{\tilde{s}_0^k\}$	informative source sentences	experts	only original question
$\mathcal{S}_i^k = \{s_i^k\}$	informative source sentences	LLM	for each $i = 0, \dots, M$
$\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_0^k = \{\tilde{p}_0^k\}$	informative source pages numbers	experts	only original question
$\mathcal{P}_i^k = \{p_i^k\}$	informative source pages numbers	LLM	for each $i = 0, \dots, M$

Human expert evaluate LLM answers only to *original* questions (i.e., indexed by 0); in particular, we ask them to rate the correctness (field \tilde{e}), choosing one of “no”, “yes, minor”, “yes, major” to: (A) Does the answer contain incorrect information? (B) Does the answer miss important information? (C) Does the answer contain irrelevant information? Examples illustrating “important”, “incorrect”, and “irrelevant” information are provided within the dataset.

Automatically-computed metrics For each original question, we compute the following *automatically assessed* metrics, with values in $[0, 1]$ where 1 represents an optimal score, using a semantic similarity function $sim(\cdot, \cdot) \in [0, 1]$:

Correctness: how similar is the LLM answer to the original question w.r.t. the expected answer

$$corr^k = sim(a_0^k, \tilde{a}_0^k); \quad (1)$$

Human-annotated correctness: we combine $\tilde{e}_A, \tilde{e}_B, \tilde{e}_C$ to generate a binary score (this is context-dependent, see definition for our use case in the Subsection 5.2), where a value of 1 stands for correct answers without false, missing, or irrelevant information

$$corr-hum^k \in \{0, 1\}; \quad (2)$$

Robustness: how similar is the LLM answer to question variations w.r.t. the LLM answer to the original question, $sim(a_0^k, a_i^k)$; we compute statistics such as the average and the standard deviation, e.g.,

$$rob_{\text{avg}}^k = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M sim(a_0^k, a_i^k); \quad (3)$$

Consistency: how similar is the LLM answer to different versions of the original question w.r.t. the expected answer; we compute statistics such as the average and the standard deviation, e.g.,

$$con_{\text{avg}}^k = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M sim(\tilde{a}_0^k, a_i^k); \quad (4)$$

Question-variability robustness: like rob_{avg} by giving larger weight to variations that are more similar to the original question

$$qv\text{-}rob^k = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M (sim(a_i^k, a_0^k) sim(q_i^k, q_0^k))}{\sum_{i=1}^M sim(q_i^k, q_0^k)}; \quad (5)$$

Explainability: how accurately do the LLM-reported information sources match the expected sources at sentence-level (as max similarity)

$$s\text{-}exp^k = \text{avg}_{\tilde{s}_0^k \in \mathcal{S}_0^k} \max_{s_0^k \in \mathcal{S}_0^k} (sim(\tilde{s}_0^k, s_0^k)) \quad (6)$$

and at page-level

$$p\text{-}exp^k = J(\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_0^k, \mathcal{P}_0^k), \quad (7)$$

where J is the Jaccard index between two sets;

Explanation robustness: how variable are the reported information sources over question variations. Like for rob^k , we compute statistics, such as the average and the standard deviation, at sentence-level

$$s\text{-}exp\text{-}rob_{\text{avg}}^k = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \left(\text{avg}_{s_0^k \in \mathcal{S}_0^k} \max_{s_i^k \in \mathcal{S}_i^k} (sim(s_0^k, s_i^k)) \right) \quad (8)$$

and at page-level

$$p\text{-}exp\text{-}rob_{\text{avg}}^k = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M J(\mathcal{P}_0^k, \mathcal{P}_i^k). \quad (9)$$

4 Use Case

In this section, we apply the methodology presented in Section 3 to the use-case of a smart wheelchair equipped with a vocal HMI to interact with their users: apart from giving commands (e.g., “slow down”), users can ask open questions about the functioning of the wheelchair.

4.1 Source document

We use the original wheelchair manual from the producer,⁶ which is an about 6 million characters long pdf, as source document. We extract text data from the document using `pdfplumber`⁷ and clean it using `cleantext`⁸ to normalize and apply to the same text encoding overall. Then, we divide the text into chunks using the `RecursiveSplitterFunction` from `Langchain`.⁹ Finally, we compute the 384 dimensional embeddings using the `all-MiniLM-L6-v2`¹⁰ transformer, which is well suited for clustering and semantic queries.

4.2 Inference

Given a question, we compute the $k = 5$ nearest chunks in the embedding space using the Euclidean distance and build the prompt as described in Section 3.1, using

an intelligent wheelchair powered by artificial intelligence that was made for helping users answer their questions

as `role` in Fig. 2. Then, we use ChatGPT (version GPT 3.5 turbo) as LLM to answer the prompt using the OpenAI API,¹¹ specifying parameters that ensure reproducibility such a constant random seed and the temperature set to 0.

4.3 Dataset

According to the criteria described in Section 3.2, we started with 171 user questions. For each user question, we automatically employ 10 data augmentation methods falling into 3 mentioned data augmentation strategies, to generate question variants:

DA Technique	Library	Based on
<i>Synonym-replacement</i>	<code>textaugment</code> ¹²	WordNet
	<code>nlpaug</code> ¹³	WordNet bert-base-uncased FacebookAI/xlm-roberta-base-nlpaug
<i>Back-translation</i>	<code>nlpaug</code>	BackTranslationAug
<i>Paraphrasing</i>	HuggingFace	prithivida/parrot_paraphraser_on_T5 tuner007/pegasus_paraphrase eugenesiow/bart-paraphrase ceshine/t5-paraphrase-paws-msrp-opinosis ceshine/t5-paraphrase-quora-paws

⁶ <https://www.ottobock.com/en-gb/wheelchairs/adults/power/juvo-b4>

⁷ <https://github.com/jsvine/pdfplumber>

⁸ <https://github.com/jfilter/clean-text>

⁹ <https://github.com/langchain-ai/langchain>

¹⁰ <https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers/all-MiniLM-L6-v2>

¹¹ <https://platform.openai.com/docs>

Note that some methods could produce more than one variant and that the same variant could be proposed by different data augmentation methods. Two human annotators were asked to check these variants and to retain only those that are: 1) correct and 2) preserving the meaning of the original questions. We consider only the variants that both annotators kept and for the final dataset we eliminated the questions with less than 8 variants. Such a high requirement in the number of variants left us with a dataset of 1168 questions out of which 92 original questions (also as some simpler questions were “variant-poor” even before the quality check).

For the different categories C , we list below the number N of questions, the average number of variants per question \bar{M} , and an example of original question:

C	N	\bar{M}	Example of original question
C1	9	11.3	Can we drive backwards?
C2	10	10.9	How often do I need to check if the wheels are securely fastened?
C3	14	12.0	How do we stop as soon as possible in case of a problem?
C4	16	12.6	What should I pay attention to?
C5	10	11.0	How should I behave in crowded spaces?
C6	11	12.3	What should I do if the green light still doesn't stop flashing even after 30 minutes?
C7	14	11.4	How to behave in case of health-related issues, such as skin problems, while using the wheelchair?
C8	8	11.5	Is it normal that the battery level changes as a bolt from the blue?

We also illustrate an example of question variations (q_0 is the original question):

q_0	How do we stop as soon as possible in case of a problem?
q_1	How do we stop as shortly as possible in case of a problem?
q_2	In case of a problem, how do we stop?
q_3	How do we stop if there is a problem?

Looking at the resulting dataset, we notice that the annotators had the least preference for variants obtained by synonym replacement methods (e.g., contextual embeddings were never chosen). On the contrary, they strongly preferred variants obtained by `Pegasus` [17], `t5-paraphrase-quora-paws` [6] and `Parrot` [1].

To compute the metrics, as similarity function, we use cosine similarity on the embeddings obtained with the same transformer model `all-MiniLM-L6-v2` used for retrieval. Finally, we had five human annotators to evaluate all questions.

5 Results

5.1 Automatic Assessment

As reported in Table 1, the overall average correctness is around 0.58. Additionally, for the overall average performance (column “All”), the highest values

¹² <https://github.com/dsfsi/textaugment>

¹³ <https://github.com/makcedward/nlpaug>

are obtained for *qv-robustness* (0.8) and *robustness* (0.798); *consistency* (0.571) is on-par with *correctness* while *explainability* metrics are low (0.251, 0.260, 0.313), with exception of *p-exp-rob_{avg}* (0.717). Lower *explainability* results stem from noisy expert annotations as well as model imperfections and underlying metrics assumptions, given that we calculate similarity between different sets of sentences, but currently assign the same weight to each sentence.

With respect to the question categories, considering all metrics, C2 has the highest scores, while C5 has the lowest. This might be expected given that C2 relates to closed-form questions where the answers are pretty clear in contrast to C5 which are open-form questions considered as difficult.

5.2 Human Assessment

We consider the answer to be acceptable if human annotators answered either with “no” or “yes, minor” to each of the questions (*A*), (*B*), (*C*) from Section 3.2 (i.e., no flaws or minor flaws in the answer w.r.t. incorrect, missing or irrelevant information). We merge flawless and minor flaws categories as these would be typically accepted by humans, for the use case at hand. Adopting this definition 47 out of total 92 questions (51.1%) have acceptable answer.

Next, we investigate whether automatic and human assessment are aligned. As can be seen from Fig. 3a, computed *correctness* scores for answers annotated as correct by human (green) tend to be higher and separable from scores for answers annotated as not correct (orange) across all categories except C6 and C8, which show no statistically significant differences. Similar considerations apply to other metrics too, like illustrated in Fig. 3b. In particular, questions with negation (C6) are problematic. Very few C1 and C2 questions are “not correct”, therefore their distribution is not informative.

Metric	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	All
<i>corr</i>	0.509	0.640	0.683	0.678	0.510	0.495	0.567	0.366	0.577
<i>corr-hum</i>	0.889	0.500	0.786	0.375	0.200	0.636	0.358	0.375	0.511
<i>rob_{avg}</i>	0.817	0.826	0.797	0.810	0.740	0.783	0.808	0.792	0.798
<i>rob_{std}</i>	0.102	0.110	0.128	0.100	0.115	0.113	0.082	0.128	0.108
<i>con_{avg}</i>	0.472	0.675	0.650	0.672	0.516	0.495	0.555	0.375	0.571
<i>con_{std}</i>	0.079	0.090	0.092	0.064	0.071	0.072	0.060	0.045	0.072
<i>qv-rob</i>	0.818	0.829	0.798	0.814	0.743	0.786	0.810	0.795	0.800
<i>p-exp</i>	0.260	0.287	0.282	0.273	0.317	0.119	0.187	0.375	0.251
<i>p-exp-rob_{avg}</i>	0.777	0.705	0.680	0.739	0.624	0.766	0.766	0.649	0.717
<i>p-exp-rob_{std}</i>	0.183	0.233	0.183	0.180	0.199	0.208	0.190	0.199	0.195
<i>s-exp</i>	0.313	0.365	0.258	0.178	0.148	0.248	0.308	0.192	0.260
<i>s-exp-rob_{avg}</i>	0.304	0.453	0.367	0.258	0.241	0.315	0.294	0.278	0.313
<i>p-exp-rob_{std}</i>	0.180	0.139	0.094	0.076	0.117	0.101	0.082	0.067	0.103

Table 1: Average results for all metrics computed over different categories. “All” denotes the average over the whole dataset.

Fig. 3: Comparison between automatically computed metrics (correctness and qv-robustness) and expert annotations (orange: “not correct”, green: “correct”).

6 Conclusions

We presented a methodology to assess the trustworthiness of an LLM-based module when answering domain-specific questions based on textual sources. We demonstrated it in a use-case where a smart wheelchair provides answers about its functioning. The results show that the model struggles with open questions and questions with negations and idiomatic expressions, and that correctness and robustness are generally better than explainability. However, rather than the results, which can heavily depend on the dataset at hand, we would like to emphasize the generalizability of our methodology. We are currently working on automatising the entire pipeline in order to avoid the need for human evaluation and permit evaluation at each step (with lower number of variants) and we are also extending the methodology to monitor the LLM answers at run-time.

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References

1. Damodaran, P.: Parrot: Paraphrase generation for nlu. (2021)
2. Es, S., James, J., Espinosa Anke, L., Schockaert, S.: RAGAs: Automated evaluation of retrieval augmented generation. In: Proceedings of the 18th Conference of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: System Demonstrations. pp. 150–158 (2024)

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3. Jang, M., Lukaszewicz, T.: Consistency analysis of chatgpt. arXiv preprint arXiv:2303.06273 (2023)
4. Johnson, D., et al.: Assessing the accuracy and reliability of ai-generated medical responses: an evaluation of the chat-gpt model. Research square (2023)
5. Jungiewicz, M., Smywiński-Pohl, A.: Towards textual data augmentation for neural networks: synonyms and maximum loss. Computer Science **20** (2019)
6. Kale, M., Rastogi, A.: Text-to-text pre-training for data-to-text tasks. In: Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on Natural Language Generation. pp. 97–102. Association for Computational Linguistics (2020)
7. Khatun, A., Brown, D.G.: Reliability check: An analysis of gpt-3’s response to sensitive topics and prompt wording. arXiv preprint arXiv:2306.06199 (2023)
8. Lewis, P., et al.: Retrieval-augmented generation for knowledge-intensive nlp tasks. Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems **33**, 9459–9474 (2020)
9. Li, J., et al.: Are you asking gpt-4 medical questions properly?-prompt engineering in consistency and reliability with evidence-based guidelines for chatgpt-4: A pilot study. npj Digital Medicine (2023)
10. Liu, Y., et al.: Trustworthy llms: a survey and guideline for evaluating large language models’ alignment. arXiv preprint arXiv:2308.05374 (2023)
11. Sennrich, R., Haddow, B., Birch, A.: Improving neural machine translation models with monolingual data. arXiv preprint arXiv:1511.06709 (2015)
12. Shen, X., Chen, Z., Backes, M., Zhang, Y.: In chatgpt we trust? measuring and characterizing the reliability of chatgpt. arXiv preprint arXiv:2304.08979 (2023)
13. Si, C., et al.: Prompting gpt-3 to be reliable. arXiv preprint arXiv:2210.09150 (2022)
14. Silva, A., Schrum, M., Hedlund-Botti, E., Gopalan, N., Gombolay, M.: Explainable artificial intelligence: Evaluating the objective and subjective impacts of xai on human-agent interaction. International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction **39**(7), 1390–1404 (2023)
15. Suárez, A., et al.: Unveiling the chatgpt phenomenon: evaluating the consistency and accuracy of endodontic question answers. International endodontic journal **57**(1), 108–113 (2024)
16. Wang, W.Y., Yang, D.: That’s so annoying!!!: A lexical and frame-semantic embedding based data augmentation approach to automatic categorization of annoying behaviors using# petpeeve tweets. In: Proceedings of the 2015 conference on empirical methods in natural language processing. pp. 2557–2563 (2015)
17. Zhang, J., Zhao, Y., Saleh, M., Liu, P.J.: Pegasus: Pre-training with extracted gap-sentences for abstractive summarization (2019)
18. Zhang, X., Zhao, J., LeCun, Y.: Character-level convolutional networks for text classification. Advances in neural information processing systems **28** (2015)
19. Zhong, L., Wang, Z.: A study on robustness and reliability of large language model code generation. arXiv preprint arXiv:2308.10335 (2023)